

SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT GOALS: OPPORTUNITIES FOR PROVIDING GENDER EQUALITY IN THE EDUCATION SYSTEM

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Abstract: In this thesis, the possibilities of ensuring gender equality in the education system are analyzed within the framework of the Sustainable Development Goals. Education is considered as an important means of achieving gender equality, issues of expanding educational opportunities for girls and women, eliminating gender stereotypes, and improving the content and methodology of education based on the principles of equality are discussed. The article analyzes the impact of ensuring gender equality on the education system, the difficulties encountered and ways to overcome them. Through this, the role and importance of education in achieving sustainable development in society is revealed.

Key words: Sustainable development, gender equality, education system, equal opportunities, gender stereotypes, girls' education, BRM, gender justice, social development, educational content.

Introduction.

Sustainable development is a complex process that includes economic, social and environmental factors. The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) adopted in 2015 are recognized as global goals set to ensure the well-being of humanity and the future of our planet [2]. Scientific research and technological innovation play an important role in achieving these goals. By systematically organizing, planning and monitoring research, countries and the international community can take more effective action towards achieving the MDGs.

One of the main principles of sustainable development is to create equal opportunities for all people. Among the 17 Sustainable Development Goals set by the United Nations, Goal 5 is aimed at ensuring gender equality and strengthening the role of women in society [3]. Gender equality is not only an expression of social justice, but also has a direct impact on the overall development of society. In this process, the education system is important and serves as the main means of eliminating gender stereotypes, creating equal opportunities and forming equal relations between women and men.

Today, the issue of gender equality in our country has risen to the level of state policy, 25 legislative documents related to the field have been adopted and the decision of the Senate of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On

approval of the strategy for achieving gender equality in the Republic of Uzbekistan" by 2030 has been adopted [1].

Ensuring gender equality in education is not limited to expanding educational opportunities for girls and women. This process includes the content, methodology and organizational aspects of education. The education system based on gender equality facilitates the achievement of social, economic and ecological aspects of sustainable development in society. This article examines the possibilities of ensuring gender equality in the education system, the problems encountered along the way, and ways to overcome them. Education based on gender equality not only reduces gender injustice, but also serves to strengthen sustainable development in society.

Discussion:

Ensuring gender equality is one of the important directions of achieving the goals of sustainable development. The education system plays a key role in this process, because through education it is possible to eliminate gender stereotypes, create equal opportunities for all groups and change social consciousness. Ensuring gender equality in education is not limited to protecting girls' and women's rights to education, but also greatly contributes to the overall social and economic development of society.

By ensuring gender equality, it is possible to improve the quality of education, attract girls to fields such as science, technology, engineering and mathematics (STEM), diversify the workforce and increase economic prosperity [5]. At the same time, gender equality in education helps to strengthen social justice and prevent gender-based violence and discrimination.

However, there are various problems in the way of ensuring gender equality in the education system. In many countries, gender stereotypes, cultural and social barriers limit the educational opportunities of girls and women. Therefore, it is important to pay attention to the following issues in ensuring gender equality in the education system.

Creating equal opportunities in education: Creating equal opportunities for girls and boys in the education system is one of the important tasks. In this process, the role of teachers, school administration and parents is very important. Gender equality can be strengthened by creating an equal environment for girls and boys in schools and providing them with access to quality education.

Teacher training: Teachers play a key role in implementing gender-based education. Therefore, it is necessary to give them in-depth knowledge and skills

on gender equality issues in teacher training and professional development programs. This helps to form concepts of equality, respect and justice among students.

Gender-sensitive curricula: It is necessary to revise the content of education from the perspective of gender equality. For this, it is necessary to pay special attention to the role of girls and women in society, their achievements and historical experiences in educational programs. Through this, students can develop the idea of valuing gender equality and getting rid of stereotypes.

Engaging girls in STEM fields: STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics) fields are important for sustainable development. Therefore, in order to attract girls to these fields, it is necessary to organize programs and activities that encourage them. This is one of the effective ways to ensure gender equality.

Eliminating gender stereotypes: Eliminating gender stereotypes is important to strengthen gender equality in the education system. For this purpose, it is possible to form the concept of gender equality in them by providing appropriate recommendations for teachers and parents, and providing information about gender issues to students.

The following information and materials were used to study the possibilities of ensuring gender equality in the education system:

UN Sustainable Development Goals documents: The UN's 2030 Sustainable Development Goals, especially Goal 4 (Quality Education) and Goal 5 (Gender Equality), are a key resource for researching this topic. These documents define recommendations and strategies for ensuring gender equality in the education system [2].

Research articles and reports on gender equality in education: Research on gender equality, research articles and reports on gender issues in education and ways to overcome them helped to enrich the discussion. Through such materials, the influence of gender equality on the quality of education, the role of teachers and the role of the educational environment in the formation of gender equality in the minds of students were studied.

The experience of national education systems: policies and practical experiences of different countries to ensure gender equality in the education system are important material. Through these experiences, various methods of ensuring gender equality in education and the results arising from them were analyzed.

Curriculum and teacher training programs: The study of curriculum, teacher training and professional development courses on the implementation of gender-sensitive educational content in schools was used as materials. Through this, it was determined what skills and knowledge are needed to ensure gender equality in the education system.

Online learning platforms and resources: Opportunities for distance education on gender equality through the use of modern technologies were also explored in the discussion. Online learning platforms play an important role in disseminating and disseminating information about gender-based education to the general public.

The above materials revealed the possibilities of ensuring gender equality in the education system and their importance in achieving the goals of sustainable development. In this way, the article created a basis for drawing conclusions about how gender equality is implemented in the educational system and its impact on the development of society.

In this article, it was analyzed that ensuring gender equality in the education system is an important factor for achieving the goals of sustainable development. Education is the main tool for eliminating gender stereotypes in society, creating equal opportunities and forming social consciousness. Ensuring gender equality improves the quality of education, increases the active participation of girls and women in economic life, as well as their access to STEM (science, technology, engineering and mathematics) fields, and increases the possibility of ensuring general well-being in society [4].

Despite the difficulties in achieving gender equality in education, significant progress can be made in this regard. In particular, positive results can be achieved through the training of teachers, the development of gender-sensitive curricula, the use of online learning platforms and efforts aimed at eliminating gender stereotypes. This article shows how important gender equality in the education system is in the social and economic development of society.

Conclusion:

Ensuring gender equality in the education system is one of the main factors for achieving sustainable development. Through gender equality, it is possible to improve the quality of education, strengthen social equality and justice. As educational opportunities for girls and women expand, their role in economic and social life will increase, and this will directly affect the overall development of society.

In order to ensure gender equality in education, it is necessary for state policy, educational institutions, teachers and parents to work together. It is possible to create an educational environment that values gender equality by revising curricula and improving the skills of teachers. Within the framework of the UN Sustainable Development Goals, focusing on gender equality is an important direction for ensuring justice and well-being not only in the education system, but also in all spheres of society. At the same time, promoting gender equality through the use of modern technologies and online platforms plays an important role in this process.

In general, sustainable development can be achieved by ensuring gender equality in the education system. It brings positive change not just for girls and women, but for society as a whole, and is an important step towards creating a sustainable, equal world for future generations.

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